

MRU Data Repository Guidelines

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Introduction

The MRU Data Repository is part of the Scholars Portal Borealis service, a network of institutional data repositories across Canada. The data repository is intended to preserve and make publicly available datasets stemming from research conducted by members of the MRU community. Open research data forms part of the larger scholarly record and aids in maintaining transparency and reproducibility in research.

The MRU Data Repository satisfies the open data requirements of most major funders and publishers. Data housed in the repository is discoverable locally and through the Scholars Portal Borealis service, as well as through numerous federated data search tools.

Eligible Depositors

Any person affiliated with MRU may deposit data in the repository so long as the dataset meets the standards outlined below. Most data deposited in the MRU Dataverse will stem from academic research, but institutional administrative data may be deposited for the purpose of making it publicly available. The same standards should be applied to both types of data.

Students

Senior undergraduate students conducting primary research may deposit original datasets in the repository. Student research data will be subject to the same standards that apply to other data. As a prerequisite to deposit, students should attend a workshop on research data management provided by the Data Librarian, individually or as part of a course.

External Researchers

External researchers may deposit data in the MRU repository if they are affiliated with MRU through research collaborations or similar partnerships. Ideally, at least one member of the MRU community will be listed as a creator of a dataset or author of an associated work of scholarship. Potential contributions that do not meet this requirement may be considered on a case-by-case basis.

Data Standards

In order to ensure that data housed in the repository are adequately preserved and potentially reusable, all submitted datasets will be reviewed for the following criteria prior to publication.

Documentation

Datasets should be described with enough detail that another researcher with a level of disciplinary expertise similar to the creator would be able to understand and use the data independently. Documentation may include the context of data collection, variable descriptions and codes, population and sample information, data processing procedures, and any other relevant information.

All datasets must be accompanied by a readme file in either TXT or PDF format. Readme files should contain information about the dataset creator, the context of data collection or dataset creation (who, where, when, what, etc.), and the licensing terms of the dataset.

Metadata

Detailed metadata helps ensure that datasets are preserved properly and can be found by others. All required citation metadata fields should be filled out as accurately as possible. It is strongly recommended that additional citation and disciplinary metadata fields are used where appropriate.

Metadata will be reviewed by MRU Library staff prior to dataset publication. Reviewers may suggest changes to metadata in the interest of preservation and discovery.

Formatting for Preservation

Dataverse supports most file formats but, when possible, datasets should be saved in file formats that support long-term preservation. Those formats differ by data type, but generally include non-proprietary, open formats. Tabular datasets in some CSV, Excel, R, SPSS, and Stata formats are automatically converted into a tab separated format upon ingest.

Files should be named clearly and consistently without spaces or special characters. Multiple files may be organized into hierarchical folders.

Ethical and Legal Compliance

Researchers are responsible for ensuring that data deposited in the repository adheres to the principles of ethical research practice. All data stemming from human research must have been cleared for collection by the MRU Human Research Ethics Board or an equivalent ethics oversight body. Researchers must make every effort to ensure that the privacy of participants is maintained. Researchers must have the consent of participants to deposit human research data in the repository. The precise terms to which participants have agreed should be included with the dataset record or as an accompanying file.

Depositors are responsible for ensuring that they have the legal right to deposit data and that the deposit of data is consistent with all applicable MRU policies. If researchers want to deposit proprietary or confidential data and have appropriate permissions, public access to those datasets may be restricted.

Completeness of Data

Deposited data may include full datasets, subsets of larger datasets, or replication data associated with the particular findings of a project. Datasets may be in raw or processed forms, but should be substantial. Tables of aggregate data, graphs, charts, and similar outputs are more appropriately suited to repositories with a broader academic scope, such as Figshare or Zenodo.

Mediated Deposit

Researchers depositing files up to 5 gb in size can self-submit datasets. All datasets will be reviewed by MRU Library staff prior to publication. Datasets will be reviewed for adequate documentation, completeness and suitability of metadata, adherence to reasonable standards of file naming and formats, and suitability of the data for the scope of the repository. The Library may contact depositors with suggested changes, and may decline datasets if they are not found suitable. The Library will not review for or reject datasets based on perceived academic quality.

Researchers wishing to deposit files larger than 5 gb or in specialized formats (e.g. shapefiles) should contact the Library prior to beginning the submission process.

Licensing and Restricted Access

Depositors may choose one of 5 licenses for each dataset. The default template applies a CC0 license (no rights reserved) to the data, but depositors may also choose to apply CC BY, CC BY-SA, CC BY-NC, or CC BY-NC-SA licenses. For more information about Creative Commons licenses, see the [Creative Commons website](#).

Public access to files within a dataset may be restricted. There are good reasons for applying temporary or permanent restrictions, including embargo periods for in-process projects, proprietary data that requires specific terms of third-party use, or for reasons of confidentiality. If files are restricted, terms of access, the process for requesting access, and access contact information should be included in the appropriate fields.

Organizing Datasets and Dataverses

Dataverses are analogous to folders. Common practice for data repositories is to place standalone datasets unstructured within the larger institutional dataverse. Adequate metadata will ensure that datasets are discoverable using standard filter and search features. Generally, sub-dataverses should be used to organize multiple datasets of a like theme or responsible

body. Sub-dataverses may be created for research groups, large research projects, locally-hosted journals, or data collections. If you would like to find out more about establishing a dataverse in the MRU Data Repository, please use the contact information on the repository home page.

Data retention

All data and metadata will be retained indefinitely. Should the repository service discontinue through a decision of either the service provider or the Library, every effort should be made to continue providing public access to deposited data using existing identifiers. In the event that a replacement service is not feasible, depositors should be notified of the change in a timely manner.

Withdrawal

When data is deposited in the repository, it becomes part of the scholarly record. Datasets receive persistent identifiers and may be cited by other researchers and authors. Researchers are strongly encouraged not to remove data from the repository except in very exceptional circumstances. Alternative remedies may include restriction of files, temporary suppression of records, and indicators of discontinuance of the dataset in the record.